

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16731648>

AFFIRMATIVE AND NON-AFFIRMATIVE TYPES OF EVIDENTIALITY IN THE SAMPLE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK FICTION

Khamraeva Makhzuna Gayratovna

DSc researcher of SSIFL

makhzuna.khamraeva@gmail.com

***Abstract.** The following article discusses the history of the emergence of the category of evidentiality, its oral and written types according to the researches and approaches of many European scientists such as Jacobson, Makarsev, Friedman, Aikhenvald, Comrie, Willet, De Lancey and others. Moreover, in the article evidentiality is said to be a linguistic toll that expresses information that the subject has seen, heard, or received from others. Furthermore, the information is provided about affirmative and non-affirmative types of evidentiality in the sample of Uzbek, Turkish, English and Kazak languages. Besides that, in the article the morphological interpretation of evidentiality as a grammatical category in the above-mentioned languages are also described.*

***Key words:** evidentiality, confirmation, non-confirmation, modality, mirativity, tense, involuntary, unexpectedness.*

***Аннотация.** В данной статье рассматривается история возникновения категории эвиденциальности, её устные и письменные виды согласно исследованиям и подходам многих европейских учёных как Якобсон, Макарецев, Фридман, Айхенвальд, Комри, Виллет, Лансей и других. Также в статье говорится что эвиденциальность – это лингвистический инструмент, выражающий информацию, которую субъект увидел, услышал или получил от*

других. Кроме того, представлена информация о подтверждённых и неподтверждённых категориях эвиденциальности на примерах узбекского, турецкого, английского и казакского языков. А также в статье описывается морфологическая интерпретация эвиденциальности как грамматическая категория в вышеупомянутых языках.

Ключевые слова: эвиденциальность, подтверждение, неподтверждение, модальность, мимативность, время, произвольность, неожиданность.

Annotatsiya: Makur maqolada evidensiallik kategoriyasining paydo bo'lish tarixi, uning og'zaki va yozma turlari haqida Yevropaning ko'plab olimlari, jumladan Yakobson, Makarsev, Fridman, Ayhenvald, Komri, Villet, Lansey va boshqalar tadqiqotlari va yondashuvlari haqida so'z boradi. Shuningdek, maqolada evidensiallik subyekt o'zi guvoh bo'lgan, eshitgan yoki boshqalardan o'zlashtirgan ma'lumotini ifodalovchi lisoniy vosita ekani haqida so'z boradi. Qolaversa, maqolada evidensiallikning tasdiqlanganlik va tasdiqlanmaganlik turlari haqida ma'lumot berilib, o'zbekcha, turkcha, inglizcha va qozoqcha misollar orqali tushuntiriladi. Maqolada, bundan tashqari yuqorida keltirilgan tillarda evidensiallikning grammatik kategoriya sifatida morfologik talqini haqida ham ta'riflar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: evidensiallik, tasdiqlanganlik, tasdiqlanmaganlik, modallik, mirativlik, zamon, ixtiyorsiz, kutilmaganlik.

INTRODUCTION. Evidentiality is a linguistic category which serves to indicate the main meaning of speech as a source of information. This means that any information, regardless of whether it is true or false, is accepted by the addressee as factual information. Evidentiality in linguistics refers to how speakers indicate the source of their knowledge or information within a statement. It's a grammatical category that specifies whether the speaker directly witnessed an event, heard about it, inferred it, or learned it through another source. Essentially, it's a way of showing how a speaker knows what they know [en.wikipedia.org].

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS. The term evidentiality was first used as an initial linguistic notion in 1957 by Roman Jakobson in his research of Balkan Slavic with the following definition: Evidentiality is a tentative designation for a verbal category, which includes three phenomena – 1) a narrative event; 2) a speech event; 3) a narrated speech event [Jacobson1990; 388].

Evidentiality is a specific linguistic category which highlights the speaker's role as a direct participant in describing a certain event or as a transmitter of someone else's speech [Makarsev 2014; 28]. Evidentiality is the set of linguistic means that expresses the information of an addressor has witnessed, heard, or indirectly assimilated from the others.

Grammatical evidentiality is developed in some languages, in which lexical units and discursive phenomena play an important role, while modality expressions and grammatical markers act as auxiliary indicators [Friedman 1988; 131].

Evidentiality is not only a grammatical category in English, but also expresses various ways of information and is always optional. In contrast, many other languages like Quechua, Aymara and Yugakir describes the speakers' specify with the main verb or the sentence as a whole for evidentiality, or offers an optional set of affixes for indirect evidentiality, and the direct or indirect is accepted regardless of whether the information stated by the addressor is right or wrong.

Evidentiality is a broad concept that refers to the nature of the evidence in a given statement and serves to express what kind of evidence it is, if any, exists in that statement. Evidentiality is a linguistic category in which the speaker is a direct participant in the description of a certain event or a transmitter of the words of others. Evidentiality is the speaker's convey of the event to others based on someone else's statement including quotation or hearsay evidence, dream (i.e. visionary evidence), conjecture, or evidence from the speaker's previous experience (a memory) [Aikhenwald 2004; 23]. For example,

Bob is hungry. – Bobning qorni och.

If someone, perhaps Bob himself, doesn't tell us that Bob is hungry, we can say the second. We can say this on behalf of someone who cannot yet speak for himself/herself; on behalf of a baby or a pet. For example,

Bob looks hungry. – Bob och ko 'rinayapdi.

Bob seems hungry. – Bob och bo 'lib tuyuldi.

Bob would be hungry by now. – Bob hozirgacha och qolgan bo 'lardi.

Bob must be hungry by now. – Bob hozirgacha och bo 'lsa kerak [Aikhenvald 2004; 25].

The term evidentiality is problematic because it refers to two related but distinct phenomena: 1) evidential meaning and 2) evidential grammatical category [Comrie 2000; 29].

It should be mentioned that in some languages as Uzbek, Turkish, Kazakh, and English, there are several grammatical devices for expressing evidential meaning, and they are often expressed by the tense of the verb, none of which falls into the verbal categories of evidentiality. In these languages, evidentiality, serve as a primary neutral category, which occupies an important place in speech at the level of the sentence or the text [Willet 1988; 53].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The verbal category of evidential meaning status or modality is expressed as a category developed in the work of Anderson (1967) and Friedman (1978). These are: 1) the categories of confirmation; 2) the categories of non-confirmation. The expression of non-confirmation can be interpreted in several ways, one of which is the interpretation of evidence. Other possible outcomes of expressing non-confirmation include involuntaryness, rhetorical questions, and admirability, which is the linguistic expression of unexpected information, in other words, awe. This wonder is sometimes called mirativity in linguistics [Johanson 2003; 278]

Aytishlaricha ertaga qor yog 'ar ekan – Uzbek

They say it will snow tomorrow – English

All of the examples cited represent unaffirmative hearsay evidentiality which express rumours.

Menimcha ertaga qor yog'sa kerak, osmonni qalit bulutlar qoplab havo sovib ketti. = *I guess it will snow tomorrow, the sky is covered with heavy clouds and the air is cold.*

Both sentences indicate affirmative information and formulate inferential evidentiality.

Bir bor ekan, bir yo'q ekan, qadim-qadim zamonda quyi o'rmon tomonda bir sariq sochli qizaloq bo'lgan ekan (Uzbek folk fairy tales) = *Once upon a time, there lived a little girl with blonde hair, towards the lower forest.*

Given examples express folklore evidentiality as they constitute affirmative evidentiality.

Scot de Lancey investigates mirativity as a sub-type of evidentiality, or at least a related category of it [De Lancey 2001; 33]. Using the sub-category of confirmation, we can combine different meanings. For example, in Uzbek, in Kazakh, in Turkish, as well as in many other genetic and regional languages, non-affirmation is primarily expressed by the past tense markers. The past tense markers often rely on markers that express non-affirmation rather than a combination of past tense and non-confirmation. For example in Uzbek Ertaga qor yog'ar emishmi?/ Ertaga qor yog'arkanmi? – non-affirmative evidentiality and epistemic modality. Bo'ying o'sib qolibdimi?! – non-affirmative evidentiality + mirativity

In the analysis of evidentiality, tense and modality are interrelated, since evidential indicators are oriented towards temporal directions. In most cases, evidentiality is determined by the acceptance of the utterance by some subject (person). For example, in Uzbek *Aytishlaricha, Apollon barcha to'qqizta Musening sevgilisi bo'lgan va ulardan birini tanlay olmay, turmushga chiqmaslikka qaror qilgan.*

Evidentiality also consists of special grammatical elements that indicate evidence. These elements can include affixes, suffixes, or loadings. In particular, in Uzbek, we deal with the modern reflexes of five morphemes. Three of them are

connected to the stem and represent the past tense: the affirmative simple past tense Uzbek -di, -ti; in English second form of the irregular verb *aql* ' or –ed which might be pronounced as [-t, -d, -id]. The unmarked (in modern languages, the perfect (completed) Uzbek -gan, converbial (verbal) past tense -ip, -ipdi, -ibdi,

Evidentiality is one of the a widely debated topics and many scholars concern that it is used as a convenient full phenomenon for the evidence and its related meanings. In general, evidentiality is used to refer to descriptive terms such as the source of information or meaning of evidence. Because it is difficult to classify, it is appropriate to call it unaffirmative evidentiality. R. Jakobson was the first to base evidentiality on a typological system and put forward the idea that written information is unaffirmative and oral information is affirmative as evidence [Jakobson 1957; 127].

Non-confirmity (also called inferentiality) systems are widespread in the Uralic and Turkic languages. These languages indicate the presence of evidence for a particular source of information; they distinguish between direct (reported) information and indirect information, i.e., information that is indirectly reported, by focusing on its acceptance by the listener. Unlike other second-type evidential systems, the indirectness marker does not indicate information about the source of knowledge: its irrelevancy whether the information comes from hearsay, inference, or perception; however, some Turkic languages distinguish between indirect and unreported indirectness, as can be seen in the following Turkic verbs: *gel-di* past tense affirmative evidentiality; *gel-miş* – non-affirmative evidentiality in the past tense.

The unmarked suffix -di in the word *gel-di* indicates the affirmative past tense, but the suffix -miş in the second word also indicates the past tense but is not-affirmative as its indirect. Because, the Turkish -miş can be translated into Uzbek with expressions such as clearly, apparently, or as I understand it. The direct past tense marker -di is unmarked or considered neutral, and it is not determined whether there is evidence to support the statement or not.

CONCLUSION. To sum up, it is worth saying that evidentiality in linguistics, in a broad sense, serves to indicate the evidential nature of a given statement; that is, to indicate whether there is evidence for a statement or not, and if so, what kind of evidence it is. In order to distinguish between the meanings of confirmation and non-confirmation in it, it is sometimes enough to know morphemes, modal verbs, or sense verbs, which are tense suffixes, and are of great importance for every researcher.

REFERENCES:

1. Aikhenvald A. (2004). *Evidentiality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. – P 23.
2. Comrie, Bernard. Evidentials: Semantics and history. In L. Johanson & B. Utahs Educations 2000. P 129.
3. De Lancey S. The Mirative and Evidentiality. - Journal of pragmatics 2001. – P 33.
4. Friedman V. “The Category of Evidentiality in the Balkans and the Caucasus.” In American Contributions to the Tenth International Congress of Slavists: Linguistics, edited by A. M. Schenker, 1988. PP 121-139.
5. Jacobson R. Shifters and verbal categories. In *On language* Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press 1957. – PP 386-392.
6. Johanson L. (2003). Evidentiality in Turkic. In A. Y. Aikhenvald & R. M. W. Dixon Educations PP. 273–290.
7. Макарецев М.М. Эвиденциальность в пространстве балканского текста. – М.: Нестор-История, 2014. – P 28.
8. Willet T.L. (1988). A cross-linguistic survey of the grammaticalization of evidentiality. *Studies in Language* 12. – PP 51-97.